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Subprime Lending: The Mirage of Homeownership

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Abstract

In the years following end of WWII, the goal of homeownership became synonymous with the American Dream. Buoyed by favorable governmental policies that encouraged low-density housing development, the American society embraced the idea of the single-family home as the embodiment of democracy. Even though the government renewed its commitment to this objective decade later, too many low-income and black and minority families were betrayed by financial institutions that encouraged subprime loans which made the American Dream a cruel illusion. Like the Great Depression of the 1930s, the 2008 economic crises forced the government to reevaluate the very concept of democracy, and governmental and individual responsibilities. Like his predecessor, President George W. Bush, President Barack Obama saw the government's role as that of protecting low-income (i.e. minority) communities from deceitful policies designed to enhance corporate profits while deconstructing families and dreams.

Keywords: globalization, sustainable development, technology innovation, fair trade policies

1. Introduction

World War II became a significant watershed in the history of this country. First, the bombing of Japan introduced the world to the destructive power of the atom, a power that still grips the world in fear. Secondly, the conflict that became known as the Cold War locked this country into an ideological, social, and political conflict with communist Russia. Even with the eventual collapse of the Soviet Union in the 1990s, there is little evidence that our version of democracy and capitalism was far superior. The 2008-2009 economic crises bore witness to that. Lastly, the end of WWII led to a significant paradigm shift as the middle-class abandoned the city in favor of newly built, but sterile and isolated, suburbs. The result was the development of the so-called American Dream of homeownership (Listokin, 2001).

Unfortunately, some dreams of the 1950s became the nightmares of the 21st century. This essay briefly reviews the historical development of Federal actions in support of housing development and suburbanization, defines and examines the practice of subprime lending, recent foreclosure data, and the impacts of subprime lending on minorities. The data indicated that government oversight is desirable in protecting low-income and minority communities from predatory lending practices that sought only the increase in shareholder profits at the expense of family and community stability.

2. Background

Of the many problems facing the United States, and President Franklin D. Roosevelt, in 1932, perhaps none was more devastating than the pervasive homelessness caused by rampant foreclosures after the 1929 stock market crash. The ensuing depression ravaged businesses and confidence in the government. While the Founding Fathers worried that a too powerful government would pose too great a threat to the principles of democracy, FDR gambled that his New Deal policies of increased government intervention would provide relief to those who needed it most.

Likewise, President Barack Obama faced a similar economic crisis in 2008. A crisis eerily similar to that faced by FDR. Even as President Obama began the daunting task of establishing policies that would ultimately correct the crises, the comparisons to FDR are warranted. Just as President Obama sought to restore American confidence in our democratic processes and government, FDR accomplished this during the 1930s by committing the government to establishing policies ensuring all Americans would be protected from homelessness.

FDR acknowledged the previous policies of "rugged individualism," where the markets dictated individual responsibility, and with little to no governmental intervention were no longer applicable given the large numbers of homeless throughout the nation. As a result, Roosevelt's New Deal paternalism established the government's role in providing safe housing. Federal legislation like the Housing Acts of 1937 and 1949 provided resources for the construction of low-income housing and other "slum" clearance programs (Hoch, 2000; Bloom, 2008).

Additionally, the Federal government committed itself to rewarding the large numbers of returning military servicemen with low-cost home loans, which eventually contributed to rapid suburbanization in the 1950s. Bolstered by President Dwight Eisenhower's support for a national system of interstate highways, the suburbanization process increased which led to new housing that significantly changed the population densities in communities throughout the country (Murphy, 1966). Interestingly, the rapid development of suburban housing led to a process described as filtering (see Figure 1), where those in the upper middle class occupied new housing, followed by the lower

middle classes now occupying their vacant housing, and finally those in the lower classes moving into the now vacant housing left by the middle class (Short, 1982).

Figure 1. The Filtering Process, Stages 1 – 3

However, the social/economic terms middle-class and suburbanization were often synonymous with white flight, a process where the white middle-class sought what they believed was a refuge from the sudden onslaught of crime and hopelessness stereotypically associated with increased numbers of minorities in the inner city. As a result, suburban communities developed new communities and school districts that were almost exclusively white.

Nonetheless, studies found that whites were not the only racial group seeking a refuge from the crime and hopelessness of the inner city. During the 1990s, the filtering process was evident in the Midwest as the new black middle-class also fled the urban core. Even though white out-migration continued to outpace black out-migration by a ratio of nearly 6:1, the implication was clear that blacks embraced the idea of suburbanization as a means to achieve the American dream of homeownership. However, what was not clear was whether or not blacks were abandoning traditionally black neighbourhoods for economic or racial reasons.

3. Subprime Loans and Foreclosures

Not surprisingly, it was during the 1990s that the practice of subprime mortgage lending increased. By definition, a subprime loan is a mortgage instrument offered to any potential borrower who does not have the credit or employment history to qualify for a standard loan at current interest rates (Bailey, et al, 2008). In 1992, Fannie Mae and Freddie Mac, as government sponsored enterprises (GSEs), focused on expanding access to home loans through the expansion of affordable lending (Pearce, 2001). As a result, subprime loans suddenly became the mortgage vehicle of choice for many lenders in low-income and minority communities, particularly black and minority communities.

Even with increasing numbers of subprime loans in the 1990s, the foreclosure rates were at levels not seen since the 1930s. Unfortunately, the problem was not restricted to any particular region of the country. In 2007, foreclosures were common in the “Rust Belt” areas of Michigan, Indiana, and Ohio, as well as “Sun Belt” states California and Arizona (Wingfield, 2007).

A case study of foreclosure patterns in the Cleveland and Cuyahoga County for the three-year period of 2005-2008 indicated results similar to the national averages. High cost subprime loans accounted for 84 percent of all foreclosed properties and a majority of those were in low-income and black neighborhoods. What was alarming about their findings was that blacks were two to three times more likely than white borrowers to be steered towards accepting subprime loans, regardless of income. Furthermore, the study also examined the spatial influence of high numbers of foreclosures in a specific neighborhood. Their conclusions indicated that high numbers of foreclosures did negatively impact surrounding property values, as much as 500 feet away (Coulton, et al, 2008).

These findings raise particular concerns in low-income and black communities where subprime loans and other predatory lending practices were pervasive. Nationally, in low-income neighborhoods, 26 percent of the homes refinanced were with subprime loans. Conversely, subprime loans were just 11 percent of the refinanced mortgages in middle-income and even less, seven percent, in upper-income communities. Even more alarming were the high numbers of subprime loans made in black communities, regardless of income levels. In 1998, 51 percent of refinanced homes were made with subprime loans, compared to only nine percent in predominantly white communities (Bunce, 2001).

Since the 1990s, numerous studies attempted to demonstrate the relationship between subprime loans and predatory lending.¹ In a study of four major metropolitan areas, Atlanta, Baltimore, Boston, and Chicago, a correlation between subprime loans and foreclosures indicates that these loans tend to be predatory since they typically end foreclosure. In Chicago and Baltimore, there were definite increases in the percentages of subprime refinanced loans, 1,636 and 1,390 percent, respectively, between 1993 and 1998 (see Figure 2). In reviewing those subprime loans that resulted in foreclosures three years later, the city of Chicago listed 30 homes in foreclosure and in 1999 that figure increased 4,623 percent to 1,417 (see Figure 3). Conversely, foreclosures by other mortgage instruments increased only 25 percent over the same period (Bunce, 2001).

Figure 2. Refinanced Mortgages using Subprime Loans

Figure 3. Residential Foreclosures by Subprime Loans

4. Minorities and Subprime Loans

As described earlier, the 1992 GSE legislation supported the department of Housing and Urban Development in making homeownership a priority for low-income families in “underserved” areas. However, since many mortgage institutions that typically offered standard rate home loans believed these areas to be exceedingly risky, it allowed other institutions to enter the market by offering primarily subprime loans backed by the government. Thus, subprime loan activity was primarily concentrated in low-income areas versus middle- and upper-income areas (Pearce, 2001).

Nationally, between 1993 and 1998, subprime loan origination increased ten-fold, from 80,000 to more than 790,000 (see Figure 4). Similarly, the value of the subprime loans also increased from \$20 billion to \$150 billion. Likewise, as previously stated, subprime loans in low-income neighborhoods were only 26 percent of all loans, compared to only 11 and seven percent in middle class and high-income communities, respectively, in 1998. However, in black communities, subprime loans accounted for over 50 percent of all mortgages in 1998, compared to only nine percent of all loans in predominately white neighborhoods (U.S. Dept. of Housing and Development, 2000).

Figure 4. Subprime Mortgage Loans

Even though the numbers of foreclosures from subprime loans were pervasive throughout the country, the racial disparities were perhaps greatest in the Deep South. In examining the subprime lending in North and South Carolina, Florida, Georgia, Tennessee, Alabama, and Mississippi, five have percentages of subprime loan origination higher than the national average of 27.3 percent (see Figure 5). Of those, Mississippi was 11 percentage points higher than the national average. Figure 6 illustrates the racial disparities which are even more obvious in these selected states as nearly 59 percent of the subprime loans were made to Blacks whereas only 21.6 percent were made to whites (Bailey, et al, 2008).

Figure 5. Subprime Lending in Selected Southern States

Figure 6. Rates of Subprime Loans Made to Black and White Borrowers in Selected Southern States

5. Homeownership: American Dream or Illusion

Since the Great Depression of the 1930s, our government established policies that protected the right to safe and affordable housing. The economic policies of the 1950s (for example, low cost fuel and low interest rates) encouraged low density home development which ultimately led to the establishment of the single-family home as the desirable American Dream. By the 1990s, the government again made homeownership a priority, but this time for those languishing in low-income communities. Unfortunately, little attention was given to the vehicle by which homeownership would be offered to these groups of families. Studies illustrate that too many mortgage lenders used subprime loans in a predatory manner which resulted in thousands of foreclosures throughout the country.

The filtering process describes the progression of one group to the vacant housing left by the next group as that group builds and occupies new housing. However, the influence of so many foreclosures forced a reversal of the filtering process as families found themselves forced to return to the communities they previously left behind. This led to intense competition for already scarce housing in lower-income neighborhoods (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. The Filtering Process, Stage 4

Nonetheless, the government's goal of homeownership for the poor and very-poor was, and is, laudable. However, the lack of government oversight (or neglect) arguably did more harm than good to many families at or near the poverty threshold. This was something FDR understood decades earlier. He courageously shifted the government's posture of limited interference in the marketplace to one of oversight and regulation. As such the government's new role was to ensure that its people did not needlessly suffer due to fluctuations in the marketplace.

Faced with similar economic challenges, President Obama embraced the concept that the government has the responsibility to protect minority communities from the policies and business practices of unscrupulous financial institutions whose only goal is to maximize shareholder profits. The 2008 financial crises were not just the result of the failed policies of Freddie Mac and Fannie Mae, even though these GSEs received more than their fair share of criticism, but the financial institutions who made homes available to those who any reasonable person would recognize as beyond their financial means to maintain. The result was not the American Dream, but merely the illusion fed by subprime loans, predatory practices, and shareholder profits.

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